

Cultivating communication proficiency: Exploring students' perceptions of native vs. non-native English-speaking teachers

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This study examines students' perceptions of Native English-Speaking Teachers (NESTs) and Non-Native English-Speaking Teachers (NNESTs) in teaching speaking skills, focusing on teaching competence, style, classroom management, cultural knowledge, and personal aspects. A series of questionnaires and interviews were administered to 20 students from the 2017 and 2018 cohorts majoring in English at Universitas Syiah Kuala. The data collected from the questionnaires were subjected to statistical analysis, while the interview data were analyzed using an interactive model approach. The results indicate that students viewed NESTs positively, appreciating their ability (a) to create a relaxed and creative classroom atmosphere, (b) to employ diverse teaching methods, and (c) to provide valuable cultural insights; they struggled with grammar explanations. NNESTs can understand students' learning needs, anticipate difficulties, and empathize with their problems despite using fewer engaging techniques. The findings suggest that NESTs and NNESTs play complementary roles in teaching speaking, with each contributing distinct strengths to the learning experience.

Keywords: Native English-Speaking Teachers; NESTs; NNESTs; Non-Native English-Speaking Teachers; Student Perceptions; Teaching Speaking

1. Introduction

Speaking is a fundamental aspect of communication, involving the use of words to convey messages effectively (Richards & Renandya, 2002). At the Department of English Education of Universitas Syiah Kuala, speaking is taught across four levels: (a) Everyday Communication, (b) Group Activities, (c) Formal Settings, and (d) Public Speaking. These courses aim to improve students' fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar, and overall communication skills, with classes conducted by both Native and Non-Native

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English-Speaking Teachers (NESTs and NNESTs). The roles of NESTs and NNESTs in teaching speaking have been widely debated. NESTs are often seen as ideal language models due to their native proficiency and cultural knowledge. However, Medgyes (2001) argued that NNESTs can be equally effective, offering relatable learning models, effective strategies, deeper grammatical understanding, and greater empathy for students' challenges. Studies on students' perceptions of NESTs and NNESTs highlight distinct strengths. Ling and Braine (2007) found that university students in Hong Kong valued NESTs for their classroom interactions and cultural insights, while NNESTs were appreciated for their teaching methods and classroom management. Similarly, Üstünoğlu (2007) revealed that NNESTs excel in teaching effectiveness and management, whereas NESTs are better at fostering classroom interactions and demonstrating positive teaching qualities.

Despite the rich body of research, a gap remains in the understanding of the students' specific perceptions in different cultural and educational contexts, such as those at Universitas Syiah Kuala. Previous studies have often focused on broader, more generalized settings, and there is a need to explore how such perceptions manifest in specific programs and institutions. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating students' perceptions of NESTs and NNESTs in teaching speaking in the Department of English Education at Universitas Syiah Kuala. By examining the views of the students from batches 2017 and 2018 through mixed-methods, including questionnaires and interviews, this research seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the perceived strengths and weaknesses of NESTs and NNESTs in this particular educational context. The central research question guiding this study is:

- What are the students' perceptions of Native English-Speaking Teachers (NESTs) and Non-Native English-Speaking Teachers (NNESTs) in teaching speaking in the Department of English Education at Universitas Syiah Kuala?

This inquiry aims to offer insights that can inform teaching practices and contribute to the ongoing discussion of the roles of NESTs and NNESTs in EFL education.

2. Background

2.1. Students' perception

Perception is the process of becoming aware of sensory stimuli (Devito, 2011) and interpreting environmental impressions (Rakhmat, 2007). Robbins and Judge (2013) identify three key elements in the process of perception: (a) the perceiver (the individual who forms the perception), (b) the object (the person

or target receiving the perception), and (c) the context (the settings in which the perception occurs). Understanding these elements is essential for evaluating how perceptions are formed and how they impact interactions and outcomes. Van Petegem et al. (2007) emphasize the importance of considering students' perceptions when assessing learning outcomes. Understanding students' perspectives on teaching approaches, materials, and assignments allows educators to adapt their methods effectively, creating a more responsive educational environment and improving learning experiences.

2.2. Teaching speaking

Speaking is a complex, productive oral skill (Bashir, 2011; Gan, 2012) involving multiple aspects: (a) content selection, (b) vocabulary choice, (c) grammar, and (d) thought expression (Boonkit, 2010). It includes physical components (Celce-Murcia et al., 2010) and requires appropriate language use in various social contexts (Renandya & Widodo, 2016). Speaking encompasses verbal and paralinguistic elements and demands pragmatic competence and sociolinguistic awareness (Pawlak & Waniek-Klimczak, 2015; Taguchi, 2015). As an essential foreign language skill, speaking in English can be challenging for students due to the need for frequent pauses (Gan, 2012). Effective communication involves interacting with various individuals (Boonkit, 2010) and considering factors such as the interlocutor, content, and language used. Proficient speakers must be aware of the topic, linguistic choices, audience, and appropriate language.

Teaching speaking involves developing students' oral communication skills through interactive processes between educators and learners (Nunan, 2015). Effective instructional strategies are crucial for maintaining student interest (Thornbury, 2012). Educators should be well-versed in speaking principles (Burns & Richards, 2012). Harmer (2015) outlines key principles: (a) providing practice opportunities, (b) encouraging mistake acceptance, (c) balancing teacher-student talk time, (d) designing diverse tasks, and (e) recognizing differences between second and foreign-language contexts. In foreign language contexts, limited target language exposure presents unique challenges, requiring specific teaching strategies (Ur, 2012).

2.3. Previous studies on NESTs and NNESTs

The definition of native English speakers has expanded beyond those who acquired English as their first language (Cook, 2016). Characteristics now include (a) early acquisition, (b) intuitive understanding, (c) fluent speech, (d) social competence, (e) accent, and (f) community connection (Holliday, 2018). Factors such as (a) linguistic environment, (b) English status in the home country, (c) exposure quality, (d) acquisition age, and (e) cultural identity also

play a role (Faez, 2011; Moussu & Llurda, 2008). Non-native speakers, who use English as an additional language, have varying proficiency levels (Mahboob, 2018). In our post-colonial globalized world where some languages including English—and also Persian (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2024)—function as a ‘lingua franca’, the distinction between native and non-native speakers has become less clear, sparking debates about their relevance in language education (Rudolph et al., 2020)—although some still insist that native speakers are role-models and points of departure (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023b) in TEFL.

The debate on NEST and NNEST advantages continues to evolve (Mahboob & Golden, 2013; Moussu & Llurda, 2008). While NESTs have linguistic advantages, this does not necessarily equate to superior teaching effectiveness (Walkinshaw & Duong, 2012). NNESTs often bring unique strengths, including personal language learning experience and enhanced sensitivity to student needs (Braine, 2013). Contemporary research recognizes that both can be highly effective educators (Moussu & Llurda, 2008). The idea of teachers as “two different species” has evolved into a more sophisticated understanding of teacher identity and effectiveness (Faez, 2011). Differences between NESTs and NNESTs include variations in (a) language proficiency, (b) teaching approaches, (c) cultural insights, and (d) strengths in various aspects of language instruction (Mahboob, 2010; Walkinshaw & Duong, 2012).

Students increasingly prioritize teaching effectiveness over native speaker status (Aslan & Thompson, 2017). Factors valued (a) include effective language learning facilitation, (b) high English proficiency, (c) strong teaching qualifications, and (d) cultural sensitivity (Kaur, 2014; Walkinshaw & Duong, 2012). A comparative study of university students in Vietnam and Japan revealed detailed views on the strengths and weaknesses of both groups of teachers (Walkinshaw & Duong, 2012). Perceived NEST advantages include (a) accurate pronunciation, (b) standard English use, (c) authentic input, and (d) engaging environments (Chun, 2014; Walkinshaw & Oanh, 2014). Challenges with NESTs include (a) difficulty understanding speech, (b) lack of local context awareness, and (c) the potential to increase student anxiety (Medgyes, 2017; Moussu & Llurda, 2008).

NNESTs are praised for (a) understanding students' challenges, (b) explaining grammar effectively, (c) sharing learning experiences, and (d) being sensitive to local norms (Mahboob, 2010; Ma, 2012). NESTs are viewed as pronunciation role models, while NNESTs are appreciated for empathy and learner-perspective explanations (Aslan & Thompson, 2017; Medgyes, 2017; Walkinshaw & Oanh, 2014). Students value NESTs for (a) authentic input, (b) cultural insights (Chun, 2014), (c) promoting communicative language use (Walkinshaw & Duong, 2012), and (d) exposure to diverse accents (Ma, 2012).

Research suggests both groups contribute valuably to language teaching. Recommendations include (a) promoting NEST-NNEST collaboration (Selvi, 2014), (b) developing inclusive hiring practices (Holliday, 2015), and (c) providing targeted professional development (Moussu & Llurda, 2008). Leveraging complementary strengths can create more effective, balanced programs catering to diverse student needs and contexts.

3. Method

This study employed a mixed-method research design to explore students' perceptions of Native English-Speaking Teachers (NESTs) and Non-Native English-Speaking Teachers (NNESTs) in teaching speaking skills.

3.1. Participants

The subjects of this study comprised 20 students enrolled in speaking classes with both NESTs and NNESTs during the academic years 2017 and 2018. These students were randomly selected to ensure a representative sample. From this group, nine students who had been taught by three different NESTs and three different NNESTs were selected for in-depth interviews. Three students were randomly selected from each teacher's class to participate in the interviews.

3.2. Instruments

In conducting the study, questionnaires and an interview guide were used to gather data. The instruments were adapted from Kasai et al. (2011). They were divided into five categories: (a) teaching competence, (b) teaching style, (c) classroom management, (d) cultural knowledge, and (e) teachers' personal aspects.

This study employed a 4-point Likert scale questionnaire designed to capture students' perceptions of NESTs and NNESTs. The questionnaire consisted of 15 close-ended questions, with students asked to rate each item on a scale from 1 to 4, where 1 indicated "strongly disagree," 2 "disagree," 3 "agree," and 4 "strongly agree." This format quantified students' opinions and provided a clear, structured means of data analysis.

Emzir (2010) and Salmani Nodoushan (2016a) define an interview as a series of prepared questions presented to a person in a face-to-face interaction, with the researchers recording the responses. In this study, open-ended interviews were conducted to allow for a more in-depth exploration of the students' perceptions. Similarly, the interview guide was structured according to the categories established by Kasai et al. (2011), resulting in five questions that specifically addressed students' perspectives on NESTs and their instruction of

speaking skills. This approach enabled the researchers to gather detailed insights into the participants' experiences and opinions, complementing the quantitative data obtained from the questionnaires.

3.3. Procedure

An online questionnaire link, created using *Google Forms*, was provided for 20 selected students from the 2017 academic year and 10 selected students from the 2018 academic year who had taken speaking classes with NESTs and NNESTs. The objectives and procedures for filling out the questionnaire were first explained to ensure that the respondents understood the importance of providing honest answers. The questionnaire included 15 questions on cultural knowledge, teaching competence, teaching style, teacher personal aspects, and classroom management.

For the interviews, nine students were selected, each having been taught by three different NESTs and NNESTs across three classes, with three students randomly chosen from each class. Interviews were conducted after they completed the questionnaires. The interview guide consisted of five questions related to NESTs and NNESTs in teaching speaking. The interviews were conducted online. The researchers used a combination of telephone calls and voice notes on *WhatsApp* to gather responses, adapting to the participants' availability and connectivity issues. This approach ensured that all students were able to participate despite external challenges. Each interview lasted between 15 and 20 minutes. To ensure the accuracy of data collection and analysis, the dialogues during the interviews were recorded.

The questionnaire data were analyzed to determine the percentage of the students who selected comparable responses. The questionnaire data were analyzed using the formula given by Sudijono (2004). For the interview data, interactive model analysis techniques described by Miles et al. (2014) were employed. Each interviewee was assigned a code (R1 to R9) to maintain confidentiality and facilitate data analysis. The qualitative data were then systematically examined to identify recurring themes, patterns, and insights into students' perceptions of their speaking classes with and without NESTs.

4. Results

A total of 20 students completed the questionnaire, which comprised 15 questions, and 9 of these students also participated in interviews, answering five questions on their perceptions of NESTs and NNESTs in teaching speaking skills. The results are thematically discussed based on the framework of Kasai et al. (2011), which includes teaching competence, teaching style, classroom management, cultural knowledge, and teachers' personal aspects.

4.1. Teaching competence

First, students' perceptions of the competence of their NESTs and NNESTs were probed. Students were asked to evaluate NESTs and NNESTs in terms of learning (a) 'effectiveness', (b) 'clarity in teaching', (c) 'ability to teach more vocabulary', (d) 'proficiency in teaching grammar', (e) and 'the extent to which practice was provided by teachers to improve students' speaking skills—i.e., items 1-5 in the questionnaire.

As for 'teacher effectiveness' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2006a, 2006b, 2007a, 2007b, 2008, 2011), it was revealed that learning speaking skills with NESTs, or 'native experts' à la Salmani Nodoushan (2023b), is more effective than with NNESTs. The results showed that 55% of the students (11 out of 20) 'agree' that learning speaking with NESTs was more effective than learning with NNESTs. Additionally, 35% of the students (seven out of 20) 'strongly agree' with this statement. Conversely, 10% of the students (two out of 20) 'disagree,' and none of the students 'strongly disagree'. This indicates a significant preference for NESTs among the students surveyed. The data from the interviews corroborate these findings. For instance, Respondent 9 stated:

In my opinion, as far as I have learned speaking with NEST, they have helped me a lot in improving my progress in speaking lessons, because we are provoked to speak as comfortably as we can and relate to simple things. [R9]

This sentiment highlights that many students believe NESTs create a 'comfortable and engaging environment' (cf. Daftarifard & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011) that encourages active speaking, thereby enhancing their speaking skills. However, some students provided contrasting perspectives. For example, Respondent 3 remarked:

NNEST helped me improve my English. Sometimes they correct any pronunciation or grammatical errors, and they explain it in Indonesian if I do not understand it. It really helps in improving my skill. [R3]

This response indicates that although many students found NESTs more effective overall, they were appreciated for their ability to address specific linguistic issues and provide explanations in the students' native language, which can be particularly helpful for comprehension and learning.

Second, clarity in teaching was also probed through the questionnaire. The respondents found Instruction by NESTs as more comprehensible than instruction by NNESTs. 65% of the students (13 out of 20) agreed and 5% (one student) strongly agreed that being taught by NESTs is more comprehensible

than being taught by NNESTs. However, 30% of the students (six out of 20) disagreed with the statement, and none of the students strongly disagreed. This distribution indicates the majority perception that NESTs are more comprehensible in their teaching methods. Supporting this observation, one student commented:

In my personal opinion, the strength of NEST is that we can learn with good and right roles, studying with NEST can make it easier for me to learn. [R7]

This statement suggests that students believe that NESTs provide clear and effective instruction (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2009a, 2023a), facilitating easier learning and comprehension. Conversely, some students prefer NNESTs because they can bridge linguistic gaps. For instance, another student noted:

NNEST can mix English and Bahasa to explain the meaning actually so it can make me easier to understand. [R2]

This perspective emphasizes the value of NNESTs' bilingual abilities, which can help students grasp complex concepts by explaining them in both English and their native language; this is in line with Salmani Nodoushan's (2016b) observation that 'L1 mediation' can be brought to bear on EFL teaching and help learners 'self-regulate' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2012) their learning and enhance their own creativity (Salmani Nodoushan, 2018).

The third issue probed by the questionnaire and the interviews was NESTs and NNESTs ability to teach more vocabulary. Our findings indicated greater vocabulary learning with NESTs compared to NNESTs. 75% of the students responded positively to the statements that asked if they learned more vocabulary with NESTs than with NNESTs. Specifically, 25% of the students (five out of 20) strongly agreed, and 50% of the students (10 out of 20) agree. In contrast, 25% of the students (five out of 20) disagreed, and none strongly disagreed with the statements. The data from the interviews also support these findings. For instance, one student stated:

NEST really helps me in enhancing the vocabulary and acquiring the language more naturally. [R5]

Another student echoed this sentiment:

I felt progress on my vocabulary and pronunciation during my learning with NEST. [R6]

These statements suggest that many students perceive learning with NESTs as beneficial for improving their vocabulary and pronunciation. The natural language acquisition environment provided by NESTs was highlighted as a key factor in their vocabulary development (cf. Nordlund & Norberg, 2020). However, some students expressed different perspectives. For example, one student mentioned the following:

In terms of vocabulary use in different contexts, I think NNEST also provides a good role model in teaching speaking. [R8]

This response indicates that although many students found NESTs effective for vocabulary acquisition, NNESTs were recognized for their ability to effectively teach vocabulary in various contexts. This appreciation for NNESTs highlights their role in providing contextually relevant vocabulary and practical language use.

The fourth dimension addressed the issue of ‘proficiency in teaching grammar’. Findings indicated that NNESTs were, overall, more effective in teaching grammar than NESTs. Nevertheless, differing opinions on this statement were observed. A total of 75% of the students responded positively, with 25% (five out of 20) choosing strongly agree and 50% (10 out of 20) choosing agree. Conversely, 20% of the students (four out of 20) chose disagree, while 5% (one out of 20) chose strongly disagree. These differing opinions were also expressed in the interview responses. Here are some varied student perspectives on this statement:

NNEST really helped my progress in terms of learning good and correct grammar and vocabulary mastery. [R1]

NEST has more advantages in terms of grammar and pronunciation; therefore, students learn and understand better grammar and spelling mistakes in English word. [R6]

The data from the interviews provide additional insights into these perspectives. One student highlighted the positive impact of NNESTs on their grammar and vocabulary mastery, indicating a preference for NNESTs in these areas:

NNEST really helped my progress in terms of learning good and correct grammar and vocabulary mastery. [R1]

In contrast, another student emphasized the strengths of NESTs in teaching grammar and pronunciation, which they found beneficial for understanding and correcting mistakes and ‘goofs’ (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018b) in English:

NEST has more advantages in terms of grammar and pronunciation; therefore, students learn and understand better grammar and spelling mistakes in English word. [R6]

These contrasting viewpoints suggest that while the majority of the students perceive NNESTs as more effective in grammar instruction, some students recognize the value of NESTs, particularly in teaching pronunciation and correcting spelling mistakes. This highlights the complementary roles of NESTs and NNESTs in enhancing students' overall language proficiency.

The fifth and the last dimension of teaching competence concerned the extent to which practice was provided by teachers to improve students' speaking skills. The findings showed that extensive practice with NESTs enhances students' English speaking proficiency. In their responses to the questionnaire items, 50% of the students chose agree, while 35% selected strongly agree, indicating a strong positive perception of the effectiveness of speaking practice with NESTs. Conversely, 15% of the students disagreed with the statement, showing a minority who do not share this positive perception. The data from the interviews provide further insights into these perceptions. Several students expressed the benefits of practicing speaking with NESTs:

At the current level of English, I think NEST is better for me because it can train me to be better in the context of Speaking. [R7]

As far as I have learned speaking with NEST, they have helped me a lot in improving my progress in speaking lessons because we are provoked to speak as comfortably as we can and relate to simple things. [R9]

These student statements highlight the perceived advantages of practicing with NESTs, including improved speaking skills and increased comfort and confidence in speaking English. They appreciated the opportunity to practice speaking in a relaxed and supportive environment which encouraged them to speak freely without fear of making mistakes.

4.2. Cultural Knowledge

This section discusses students' perceptions of NESTs and NNESTs regarding their cultural knowledge of English-speaking countries when teaching in the classroom. Students provided their opinions on NESTs and NNESTs in terms of (a) sharing knowledge about the culture of English-speaking countries, and (b) assessing NESTs' extent of knowledge about the culture of English-speaking countries.

Our findings showed that NESTS enhance students' cultural understanding of English-speaking countries in the classroom. A significant majority of the

students had positive perceptions of NESTs when they shared cultural information about English-speaking countries in the classroom. Specifically, 50% of the students (or 10 students) chose strongly agree, and 45% (or nine students) chose agree, making a combined total of 95% of the students who appreciate the cultural insights provided by NESTs. Only 5% of the students (or one student) disagreed with the statement, indicating a minority view that NESTs do not frequently present cultural information in class. The interview responses corroborated the questionnaire results, highlighting the value students placed on cultural information shared by NESTs. One student remarked:

[A] NEST comes from countries with English as their national language; at the same time, they know more and better about cultural information. [R6]

This statement highlights the perception that NESTs, who are native speakers, have a deeper and more authentic understanding of cultural nuances that they can effectively convey to students. However, not all students shared this view. One student noted that NNESTs also contribute valuable cultural insights:

Lots of NNEST[s] share their experiences while they are studying abroad and share the culture shock they had while studying there. [R8]

This perspective suggests that NNESTs, through their personal cultural immersion and adaptation experiences, can also provide meaningful cultural information that enriches students' learning experiences.

As for assessing the cultural knowledge of NESTs regarding English-speaking countries, the results of the questionnaire indicated that the majority of the students perceived NESTs as knowledgeable about the cultures of English-speaking countries. Specifically, 45% of the students (or nine students) selected agree, and 40% (or eight students) chose strongly agree, reflecting a strong consensus that NESTs have a robust understanding of cultural aspects. Conversely, 15% of the students (or three students) chose disagree, while none of the students chose strongly disagree. These data suggest a general agreement among students regarding NEST cultural expertise. The interview responses supported these findings. One student expressed the following:

I would say NEST because they surely know better about the culture because they are a native. [R5]

This statement stresses the belief that, by virtue of their native background, NESTs have authentic and in-depth knowledge of the cultures of English-

speaking countries. However, there is a contrasting opinion from another student:

NNEST because NNESTs study abroad and often talk about the cultures that live there. [R4]

This perspective highlights that NNESTs, through their own experiences studying abroad, also provide valuable cultural insights and discussions about the cultures they have encountered.

4.3. Classroom management

This section examines students' perceptions of native and non-native teachers' classroom management. Students were asked about (a) the methods and techniques used by NESTs and NNESTs in the teaching and learning process, and (b) whether the classroom atmosphere with NESTs and NNESTs was flexible and fun.

Concerning the former, the questionnaire results revealed varied opinions on the effectiveness of teaching methods and techniques used by NESTs compared to NNESTs. According to the data, 60% of the students ($n = 12$) agreed that the methods and techniques used by NESTs were superior. Conversely, 25% of the students (or five students) disagreed with this view. 10% of the students (or two students) chose disagree, and only 5% of the students (or one student) selected strongly disagree. These results suggest that a significant majority of the students—i.e., 85%—perceive NESTs' methods and techniques as more effective in the teaching and learning process. The interview responses further demonstrate the diversity of opinions. One student stated:

NEST because when teaching in the classroom, they provide many teaching methods, and we are more free to speak. [R4]

This comment highlights the perceived advantage of NESTs in offering various methods that encourage more interactive and flexible speaking practice. In contrast, another student remarked:

For NNEST, there are several lecturers who also provide interesting methods that can improve our speaking skills. [R4]

This statement indicates that NNESTs also employ engaging methods that contribute positively to students' speaking skills. Overall, while most students favor the methods and techniques of NESTs and recognize them as more effective, there is an acknowledgment of the valuable teaching approaches used by NNESTs.

As for flexibility and engagement of classroom atmosphere, our results indicated a strong positive perception of the class atmosphere in NEST lessons. According to the data, 95% of the students reported that their NEST classes were more flexible and enjoyable. Specifically, 55% of the students (or 11 students) chose strongly agree, while 40% (or eight students) chose agree. In contrast, only 5% of the students (or one student) disagreed with this statement. This significant disparity highlights the consensus that NEST classes offer more engaging and relaxed environments than classes with NNESTs. The interview responses further support this finding. One student shared:

The native speaker teaching is really fun because, before the class starts, they sometimes give us new knowledge like idioms, play games, and conduct easy quizzes. [R3]

This response highlights the diverse and enjoyable activities that NESTs incorporate into their teaching, which contribute to a positive and dynamic class atmosphere. However, another student provided a contrasting view:

NEST has fewer methods to make the class more active, fun, and controlled. [R9]

This comment suggests that while NEST classes can be viewed as more flexible, there are also concerns about the level of control and variety of activities compared to NNEST classes.

4.4. Teaching style

The fourth dimension of the current study concerned students' perceptions of the teaching styles of their native and non-native English-speaking teachers. Students responded to the questionnaire based on their classroom experiences with NESTs and NNESTs, focusing on (a) whether these teachers frequently used a variety of materials such as videos, audio, songs, and games and (b) whether they incorporated group or pair activities into their lessons.

Concerning the variety of instructional materials provided by NEST and NNEST, our findings revealed varied perceptions among students regarding the variety of materials provided by NESTs. 50% of the students ((or 10 students) indicated agree with the statement, while 40% of the students (or eight students) selected strongly agree. Conversely, 5% of the students (or one student) chose disagree, and another 5% selected strongly disagree. This indicates that most students believe that NESTs offer a broader range of instructional materials (such as videos, audio, songs, and games) than NNESTs. This finding was corroborated by the interview responses which highlight the diverse teaching methods used by NESTs:

Based on my experience, NESTs are better role models in English because they incorporate fun learning methods, including games, role plays, and videos, making the lessons less monotonous. [R6]

However, there was a dissenting opinion:

Sometimes NNESTs also start the class with games related to the learning materials. [R1]

This student feedback suggests that while NESTs are perceived to provide a greater variety of materials, they also use engaging methods to enrich their lessons.

As for the frequency of group and pair activities with NESTs and NNESTs, the analysis of the student responses revealed a diverse range of opinions. 40% of the students (or 8 students) indicated that they 'agree' with the statement, while 15% of the students (or 3 students) chose strongly agree. This suggests that a segment of the students experience more group or pair activities with NESTs.

However, there is a notable counterview. 40% of the students (or eight students) selected 'disagree', and 5% of the students (or one student) chose strongly disagree. These responses indicate that they perceive NNESTs as providing a similar or greater amount of group or pair activities. These varied perceptions were further reflected in the structured interviews. Students provided differing perspectives on the frequency and quality of group/pair activities with and without NESTs:

I think NEST uses various methods in teaching speaking compared to NNEST. NESTs employ more fun and flexible teaching activities, such as group activities and games, which are also well-managed. [R8]

Conversely, another student highlighted a different experience:

Based on my experience in speaking class, NNESTs consistently provide opportunities to practice speaking in pairs or groups during nearly every session, which I find very enjoyable. [R2]

Overall, while a portion of the students felt that NESTs incorporated more group or pair activities, a significant number of the students also recognized that NNESTs offered frequent opportunities for collaborative speaking exercises.

4.5. Teachers' personal aspects

This final section of the results explores students' perceptions of their native and non-native teachers' personal attributes. Students were surveyed on their views regarding which type of teacher (a) better understands their needs, (b) is more capable of anticipating learning difficulties, (c) shows greater empathy toward learning problems, and (d) is perceived as nicer and more responsible. These personal traits represent what Pashapour and Salmani Nodoushan (2016) have called 'true professionalism'.

As for the students' perceptions of NNESTs' and NESTs' understanding of their students' learning needs, our study results indicated a strong belief held by students that, compared to NESTs, NNESTs have a better understanding of their students and their learning needs. 70% of the students (or 15 students) held this view. Specifically, 50% of the students (or 10 students) selected 'agree' in their responses to the questionnaire; an additional 25% of the students (or five students) chose strongly agree. Conversely, 25% of the students (or five students) expressed a different opinion. This category included 20% of the students (or four students) who selected 'disagree', and 5% of the students (or one student) who chose 'strongly disagree'. This suggests a minority perception that NNESTs may not understand students' needs better than NESTs. These findings show a consensus that NNESTs are perceived as more attuned to student needs although a notable minority harbor opposing views.

A second dimension of teachers' personal aspects concerned the ability of NNEST and NEST to anticipate students' English language difficulties. Our results revealed that most of the students believe NNESTs are more adept at anticipating difficulties when learning English. 65% of the students (i.e., 13 of them) selected 'agree', and 10% (or two students) chose 'strongly agree'. In contrast, 20% of the students (or four individuals) chose 'strongly disagree' indicating that these students feel that NNESTs may not be as effective in anticipating their learning challenges. This suggests that a substantial proportion of the students acknowledge that NNESTs can address learning.

A third dimension of teachers' personal aspects concerned the empathy of NNEST and NEST towards students' learning challenges. The responses revealed a diverse range of opinions regarding the empathy of NNESTs compared to NESTs. According to the data, 45% of the students (or nine individuals) indicated 'agree', and 20% (or four students) selected 'strongly agree', suggesting that they perceive NNESTs as demonstrating greater empathy toward their learning difficulties. Conversely, 30% of the students (or six individuals) chose 'disagree', and 5% (or one student) selected 'strongly disagree', indicating that they feel NESTs may be more empathetic toward their learning problems. This suggests that, while nearly half of the participants

viewed NNESTs as more empathetic, a significant portion believes that NESTs show a greater understanding of their learning challenges.

The last dimension of teachers' personal aspects concerned NNEST and NEST professionalism and responsibility in language education. The analysis of the students' perceptions of their teachers' personal qualities returned overwhelmingly positive feedback. According to the data, 90% of the students (i.e., 18 participants) rated NESTs positively for being 'nice' and 'responsible'. Specifically, 55% of the students selected 'agree', and 35% chose 'strongly agree' on this statement. Conversely, only 5% of the students (or one individual) indicated 'strongly disagree', suggesting that a very small proportion disagrees with the notion that NESTs are nice and responsible. These results indicate a strong consensus among students showing that NESTs are perceived as both kind and accountable—reflecting a high level of student satisfaction with teachers' personal qualities.

5. Discussion

The findings of this study offer a perspective on students' perceptions of NESTs and NNESTs in speaking classes at the Department of English Education of Universitas Syiah Kuala, Indonesia. While students generally responded positively to NESTs, they also recognized the unique strengths of the NNESTs, suggesting that both groups of teachers play crucial roles in nurturing and cultivating students' communication proficiency.

Concerning teaching competence, the respondents perceived NESTs as more effective for teaching speaking, citing increased confidence and immersive English environments that enhance fluency and vocabulary acquisition (cf. Ellis, 2005; Lasagabaster & Sierra, 2005). NESTs were associated with authentic language use (cf. Medgyes, 2021) and interactive teaching methods (cf. Sung, 2014). However, NNESTs were seen as more effective for teaching grammar due to their experience learning English as a second language, allowing for a more analytical approach (cf. Moussu, 2018). Some students preferred NNESTs for their better preparation and understanding of the learning process, creating a more empathetic environment (cf. Lee, 2020). The findings suggest that both NESTs and NNESTs bring unique strengths to the classroom, with NESTs excelling in creating authentic language environments and NNESTs providing valuable insights into the language learning process. This supports a more inclusive approach to English language teaching (cf. Matsuda & Matsuda, 2017).

In terms of cultural knowledge, the respondents generally perceive NESTs as having a more comprehensive and authentic understanding of English-speaking cultures. This aligns with Barratt and Kontra's (2000) assertion that NESTs bring firsthand cultural experiences to the classroom. Students

reported gaining up-to-date cultural insights from NESTs, who often shared personal experiences and drew comparisons between their home and Indonesian cultures. However, it is noteworthy that some students recognized the cultural knowledge of NNESTs, particularly those who had studied or lived in English-speaking countries. This observation supports Medgyes's (2017) argument that NNESTs can serve as cultural mediators, bridging the gap between the target culture of the students and their own cultural background. The ability of NNESTs to highlight unique or fascinating cultural aspects suggests a valuable perspective that can enrich students' cultural learning experiences. Galloway and Rose (2018) further emphasized the importance of exposing students to diverse 'World Englishes' and cultural perspectives—which both NESTs and NNESTs can contribute to (cf. Bhatia & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Brown and Salmani Nodoushan, 2015; Johns & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015).

Regarding classroom management, the respondents generally perceived NESTs as creating more engaging and flexible learning environments. NESTs were reported to employ diverse techniques, including daily idiom introductions, interactive games, and regular quizzes. This approach aligns with Harmer's (2007) emphasis on the importance of variety and engagement in language classrooms. This also resonates with Dörnyei and Kubanyiova's (2014) emphasis on creating a motivating classroom atmosphere to enhance language learning. The interactive nature of NEST-led classes appears to facilitate students' grasp of the material, echoing Krashen's (1982) theory of comprehensible input in language acquisition. Nevertheless, NNESTs were also recognized for their classroom management skills, with some students noting increased discipline in NNEST-led classrooms. This observation resonates with Moussu and Llorca's (2008) findings that NNESTs often maintain stricter classroom environments that benefit certain learning objectives and student preferences.

Nevertheless, NNESTs were also recognized for their classroom management skills, with some students noting increased discipline in NNEST-led classrooms. This aligns with Moussu's (2018), who found that NNESTs often maintain stricter classroom environments, which can benefit certain learning objectives and student preferences. Furthermore, Mahboob and Lin's (2016) work on the strengths of NNESTs highlights their ability to anticipate and address specific linguistic challenges faced by learners with first-language backgrounds.

In terms of teaching style, the findings revealed that the students overwhelmingly perceived Native English-Speaking Teachers (NESTs) as providing a more diverse range of instructional materials and methods. NESTs frequently incorporate multimedia resources such as videos and audio clips,

employ interactive 'games' (Ghahraman & Shabani, 2021; Salmani Nodoushan, 2009b), and conduct learning activities outside the traditional classroom setting. This variety of teaching approaches aligns with Dörnyei and Kubanyiova's (2014) emphasis on creating motivating classroom atmospheres to enhance language learning. Both NESTs and NNESTs are reported to frequently organize student activities in groups or pairs, particularly in speaking classes. This collaborative approach facilitates speaking practice and aligns with contemporary communicative language teaching methodologies.

Regarding personal teaching aspects, the respondents perceived NNESTs as more attuned to their learning needs and better equipped to anticipate learning difficulties in speaking classes. This finding resonates with Mahboob and Lin's (2016) work, which highlights NNESTs' ability to anticipate and address specific linguistic challenges faced by learners with first-language backgrounds. Students reported that NNESTs demonstrated high empathy toward their learning challenges, which is consistent with Moussu's (2018) findings on the strengths of NNESTs in maintaining supportive classroom environments. This is further supported by previous research, such as Demir's (2011) study, which found that students had more favorable impressions of NNESTs due to their empathetic understanding of the challenges involved in learning a foreign language. This empathy stems from NNESTs' personal experiences as language learners, allowing them to relate more closely to their students' difficulties and provide targeted support.

6. Conclusion

This study examined students' perceptions of NESTs and NNESTs in teaching speaking skills at Universitas Syiah Kuala. Findings revealed positive responses to NESTs for improving speaking skills and creating engaging environments, while NNESTs were perceived as more proficient in explaining grammar and understanding students' difficulties. These results align with previous research, suggesting both NESTs and NNESTs can be effective teachers with unique strengths. The study's implications include the need for comprehensive teacher training, collaborative teaching models, enhanced cultural awareness for NESTs, and improved grammar instruction techniques.

However, this study has several limitations, including its small sample size, geographical constraints, focus on speaking skills, reliance on self-reported data, and limited exploration of factors influencing perceptions. Future research should address these limitations through larger-scale studies across multiple institutions and countries, investigating other language skills, incorporating mixed-method approaches, and exploring factors influencing students' perceptions to inform evidence-based practices in English language education.

Authors' statements

Diana Achmad contributed to sections 1, 2, 3, and 4 of the manuscript. Saiful Marhaban worked on sections 5 and 6 of the article. Cut Rina Elsa Fitrianty assisted in data collection and reference checking. Lily Ping Li helped proofread the article.

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